

INTERPRETATION OF THE PROBLEM OF HUMAN AND BEING IN ERNEST HEMINGWAY'S WORK

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Annotation: At the stages of education, drawing a literary work into an artistic-aesthetic analysis is creating a unique interpretation. Where there is no real artistic analysis, the artistic text does not affect the feelings of the reader and does not serve to form his spirituality. This article analyzed the interpretation of the problem of human and being in the works of Ernest Hemingway

Keywords: artistic-aesthetic analysis; stories and novels; human.

Ernest Hemingway is one of the most famous novelists all around the globe. He has written many books and “The Old Man and the Sea” stands out at the top. The book had fetched him both the “Pulitzer Prize” and “Nobel Prize” in 1953 and 1954 respectively. The book has got lots of natural elements present in it. The way the author presents nature is quite marvelous, catchy and signifies a lot of importance. The importance of nature in the life of human beings is beautifully shown and presented in the novel. The word used by the author is simple, direct and easy to understand. Ernest Hemingway is one of the most powerful short story writers and novelist of America. Most of his stories and novels are based upon his personal experiences. He occupies a prominent place in the American Literary history for his never ending role in the areas of fictional writings. Hemingway has written in a simple but unconventional style, with the problems of war, hatred, violence, relationship of man towards nature and death as the themes. His novels present a symbolic interpretation of human life.

The author through “The Old Man and Sea” makes a realization to the readers that man is a part of the whole universe. Further, man, fish and all other creatures in

nature are similar from the cosmic point of view. Though man may not treat other creatures as same, but to the universal conscience that treats man and other creations of nature as equals. The story is a presentation of life as a struggle against the indestructible and unconquerable forces in which a kind of victory is possible. With the novel, Hemingway had written an epic metaphor for life. The fish is the creation of the natural world with its ambiguous and unbreakable essence. It can't be taken home as a trophy of some tournament. In the struggle between life and death, the problem of right and wrong seems meagre. Hemingway is a great writer. The way he portrays his natural phenomenon in his books are simply marvelous. He has a great skill of writing, his choice of selection of landscapes in different books is good and above all of this his writing mainly deals with his personal experiences. He was indeed a complete wizard of natural setting in most of his works. Due to this he can also be called as a natural writer.

When you grasp that the human condition is a never-ending cycle of ups and downs, happy and sad times, triumphs and tragedies, it removes some of the sting from the painful events. Plus, it helps bring you into the present moment instead of dwelling on what might have been. Indeed, in Hemingway's work, as Nelson Algren observes, it seems "as though a man must earn his death before he could win his life." However, it would be a mistake to allow what may appear to be Hemingway's preoccupation—or, to some, obsession—with death to obscure the fact that he is, above all, concerned in his fiction with the quality of individual life, even though it must be granted that the quality and intensity of his characters' lives seem to increase in direct proportion to their awareness of the reality of death. Despite our problems with these and other aspects of Ernest Hemingway's world-view, his works remain a rite of passage for many of today's readers and writers. Again, this is because he is such an influential stylist, but also, I believe, because the aspects of his work that give us pause are the ones that challenge us to figure out where we stand on such issues and why. Given this, I don't doubt that 10 or 20 years from now we'll be re-evaluating his work once again. For though Papa may not be the literary idol he once

was, he's still a very important writer because of what he tells us about his times, and our times as well.

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